

How forest matrix can enrich biodiversity in the natural forest remnants of Bangladesh?

Md Mizanur Rahman

Information and Communication Technology Division, Bangladesh

E-mail: rahmanboku@gmail.com

Abstract

Massive deforestation caused the fragmentation of natural forests in Bangladesh. Landscape restoration requires the management of forest patches in a spatially and temporally dynamic landscape matrix. Therefore, the study aimed to explore how the forest matrix can enrich the depleted biodiversity in the natural forest remnants. Empirical data were collected from focus group discussions and key informant interviews. The study revealed that the fragments or remnants of natural forests can maintain connectivity with the neighbouring fragments through the matrix, which can play the role of a corridor for the movements of wild animals across the landscape. It reduces the edge effects on the threatened species and can protect them from extinction. Matrix can influence the biodiversity patterns in the mosaics and the vegetation-wildlife relationship. It is highly important to give major attention to matrix management for enriching biological diversity.

Keywords: Habitat fragmentation, remnants, mosaics, matrix, extinction, corridor, edge effect

Introduction

The United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (2001) defined forest as an area of more than 0.5 ha of land with 10–30% cover of plants which can reach 2–5 m height at maturity. It includes the plant coverage with rattans, bamboo and palms subject to meeting the criteria of canopy cover and height (Lorenz & Lal 2009). The forest also includes forest roads, meadows, windbreaks, firebreaks, shelterbelts, corridors of trees, and other small open areas (Lund 2002). Forest matrix comprises landscape areas that are not primarily managed for the conservation of natural ecosystems, ecological processes, and biodiversity regardless of their current condition, whether they are natural or developed (Lindenmayer & Franklin 2002). Landscape restoration requires the management of forest patches in a spatially and temporally dynamic landscape matrix (Chazdon *et al.* 2016; Schmiegelow & Mönkkönen 2002; Martensen *et al.* 2017).

Massive deforestation caused the fragmentation of natural forests throughout the world (Laurance & Bierregaard 1997; Joly *et al.* 2014; Bradshaw 2012). Fragmented forests are composed of small patches (Magura *et al.* 2001; Santo-Silva *et al.* 2016). Overpopulation pressure and widespread poverty caused massive forest fragmentation and biodiversity loss in Bangladesh (Rahman *et al.* 2009; Rahman 2021; Rahman 2023 a-g). Habitat degradation is the main threat to achieving sustainability and green growth in Bangladesh (Rahman 2023 h, i). Therefore, the study aims to explore how the forest matrix can enrich the depleted biodiversity in the natural forest remnants.

Methodology

The secondary data were reviewed to develop a conceptual framework for the study. A Focus group discussion was carried out incorporating the respondents from diverse stakeholders like foresters, conservationists, botanists, zoologists and environmentalists. A total number of 10 key informants were interviewed to understand how Bangladesh improve the health of the forest matrix. Content analysis was done to interpret the data.

Establishing terrestrial connectivity and corridor

The respondents opined that the fragments or remnants of the natural forests of Bangladesh maintain connectivity with the neighbouring fragments through the matrix. The level of

biodiversity is influenced by the patches' size, continuous vegetation covers, and connectivity. They also added that the matrix plays the role of a corridor for the movements of wild animals across the landscape. Matrix also influences the edge effects of forest fragments. The surrounding environments have extensive effects on vertebrate communities residing inside the forest fragments. The primary forest species can use a matrix for migration in the nearby bigger patches. Some primary-forest species can use matrix habitats for reproduction as well. The vulnerability of species in fragments depends on their ability to use a matrix. A threatened species of fragments may colonize the matrix. Scattered trees can act as a bridge between the patches.

Maintaining population dynamics and ecosystem functioning

The respondents opined that a healthy matrix can save small populations, collapsed metapopulations and endangered individuals from the edge effects and extinction. It was noted that in Bangladesh, most of the natural forests are comprised of a mosaic of patches with various levels of degradation and compositional disparity. A matrix can influence the biodiversity patterns in the mosaics and the vegetation-wildlife relationship. The surrounding matrix can support the plant populations of the remnants by facilitating seed dispersion and acting as a temporary habitat. The matrix can provide food resources, resting sites and even breeding areas to frugivores. Seeds in unconnected patches suffer stronger predation than those located in connected patches. The respondents also added that seed recruitment rates are lower in unconnected patches, which can collapse natural regeneration.

What to do in Bangladesh?

The respondents admitted that the future biodiversity in Bangladesh will largely depend on how the matrix is managed. It is highly important to give major attention to matrix management for enriching biological diversity. The multiple roles of the matrix in management programmes should be realized by the managers and the policymakers. Improvement of the matrix quality may lead to higher conservation returns than increasing and manipulating the size of the fragments. Resource allocation for the matrix is fundamental to the conservation of biodiversity.

Woodlot Plantation forests should be managed for supporting local livelihoods, biodiversity conservation, and environmental services, including carbon capture and storage rather than timber production. For biodiversity conservation, emphasis should be given to managing the landscape as

a continuum of patches, corridors, and matrices. Further studies on the relationship between patch occupancy, patch area and isolation should be carried out.

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